

Ministero per i Beni e le Attività Culturali
Direzione Generale per i Beni Librari e gli Istituti Culturali

Comitato Nazionale per le celebrazioni
del centenario della nascita di Enrico Fermi

Proceedings of the International Conference
“Enrico Fermi and the Universe of Physics”

Rome, September 29 – October 2, 2001

Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei
Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare

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2003 ENEA
Ente per le Nuove tecnologie, l'Energia e l'Ambiente
Lungotevere Thaon di Revel, 76
00196 - Roma

ISBN 88-8286-032-9

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Fermi toward Quantum Statistics (1923-1925)

There are some uncertainties about the influences that might have led Fermi to the formulation of quantum statistics. Like already remarked by F. Rasetti, little is known about the circumstances that led the great Italian physicist to one of his most important theoretical contributions. It can be said that the “preparatory role” of two works by Fermi (the one about Stern’s method for the calculation of the entropy constant of a perfect gas and the other on the quantization of systems containing identical particles) is unanimously recognized. Based on a recent historical reconstruction, it will be shown how some circumstances pushed Fermi to tackle these problems. It seems that Göttingen’s environment had a strong influence on his work. We will also try to specify the time of the quantum statistics formulation.

Fermi verso la statistica quantica (1923-1925)

Sussistono alcune incertezze circa le influenze che possono aver indirizzato il percorso di Fermi verso la formulazione della statistica quantica. Come già sottolineato da F. Rasetti, poco è noto delle circostanze che hanno condotto Fermi a uno dei suoi più importanti contributi teorici. È comunque unanimemente riconosciuto il ruolo preparatorio di due lavori del giovane fisico romano, riguardanti il metodo di Stern per il calcolo della costante dell'entropia di un gas perfetto e la quantizzazione di sistemi contenenti particelle identiche. In base ad una recente ricostruzione storica, saranno mostrate le circostanze che spinsero Fermi ad affrontare questi problemi. L'ambiente scientifico di Gottinga sembra aver avuto una forte influenza sui due suoi lavori preparatori. Si cerca inoltre di precisare la collocazione temporale della formulazione della statistica quantica.

The anomalous case of Enrico Fermi, in comparison with the international scientific context of the early twenties, is evident since his first works. The young scientist Fermi behaved as an outsider fairly proud of his independence, mainly because of his strong personality. The Italian scientific environment too forced him to a self-teaching method and a cut off position. Nevertheless, it must be said that Fermi never much complained about it.

In particular, the genesis of his eponymous quantum statistics gives an interesting trail to outline, at the same time, his personality and the way, generally not well known, he followed to reach a result that put a final seal on his fame at an international level. The high level of the about thirty works from 1921 to 1926 shows a precocious technical talent. Moreover, the existence of a defined scientific style and a tendency to concentrate himself on personal research programs was already clear. Furthermore, the young Fermi had great competence in various fields of physics and an uncommon interest for both the theoretical and experimental aspects.

The theoretician Fermi, although confident in old quantum physics, was not very interested in the formulation of new principles. He was rather in search of applications that descended from those principles. That explained his pragmatic use of mathematics of which, nevertheless, he had a total mastery.

The roots of this “modus operandi” should also be searched in the pre-university years, when all the main features of his scientific personality were already emerging.¹ Anyway, it was only after his two stays in Germany (Göttingen) and the Netherlands (Leyden) that Fermi started to become aware of his value and what kind of physics was produced in the ‘sacred’ places. These two stays abroad were useful to Fermi also for the many prestigious people he met there (Born, Ehrenfest, Goudsmit, Heisenberg, Kronig, Uhlenbeck, etc.). Moreover, unlike what asserted up to now (mainly by Segrè), this work will point out the scientific importance of the influence of the German stay on Fermi.

Always devoted to a major clarification and simplification of subjects, he shuns any possible technical virtuosity and not strictly necessary hypotheses. This is evident especially in the formulation of his quantum statistics.

The key point of Fermi’s discovery (typical of his way of proceeding) lies in the bold application of Pauli’s principle to the quantization of the perfect gas, that was at the time a fairly distant problem. Fermi’s approach, here

¹ Cmp. SASSI, SEBASTIANI (1999).

defined as ‘analogy method’, is present also in other significant theoretical contributions. These results are due to Fermi’s great ability to profitably put in relation concepts that differ greatly.

However, Fermi’s article didn’t provoke any reaction, at least until Dirac came to the same results. The silence from the scientific community was mainly justified by Dirac’s larger fame and powerful use of the new quantum concepts, that allowed in-depth explanations of the subject studied.² In his article on the new quantum statistics, Fermi also introduces an harmonic potential to contain atoms of the gas. That could be considered as an unnecessary complication, but there are also some interesting motivations for this unusual choice. In any case, later on, the harmonic potential was abandoned even by Fermi.

The years before Fermi’s quantum statistics

The beginning of the twenties, as it is known, was a crucial period for physics. S. Goudsmit humorously described the physics community of the time: “The concept of the ‘good old days’ does not apply [...] In the 1920’s, by comparison, we lived in a small village with its little feuds, a Peyton Place without sex”.³

The “Peyton Place without sex” it’s a nice metaphor to illustrate the anxiety of those managing quantum physics, that were getting few gratifications and many disappointments. The few that, like Fermi in Italy, were devoting themselves to the new physics, were considered to all intents and purposes like “sinners”.⁴

From January to August 1923, he stayed eight months in Germany, at Göttingen, with Max Born, without much advantage, according to Segrè.⁵ Later, from September to December 1924, Fermi spent four months in Holland, at Leyden, with Paul Ehrenfest. This shorter period of study was, as for human relations, much more satisfactory. The two stays abroad had a

² “[...] playing with symmetrical and anti-symmetrical functions, Dirac derived both quantum statistics in one stroke. [...] Fermi had in fact derived ‘only’ his statistics”, *cmp.* BELLONI (1994), p. 107.

³ *Cmp.* GOUDSMIT (1976).

⁴ Actually, Fermi was almost the sole ‘sinner’. Rasetti reports that: “By 1920 or even ‘22, quantum theory in Italy was essentially confined in Fermi’s mind and there was very little outside. For instance, I first heard of the quantum theory and Planck’s constant from Fermi”, *cmp.* A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T. S. Kuhn with F. Rasetti and E. Persico, 8 April 1963, p. 8.

⁵ *Cmp.* F.N.M., p. XXVI-XXVII.

great influence on Fermi. They can be considered as his first direct encounter with “modern” physicists and with two places extremely favourable to the scientific activity.⁶

It was also Fermi’s first opportunity to get to know the culture, politics and social organisation of two countries very different from Italy’s at the time: “[...] he said that he found everything so superior to what he was used to in Italy in every respect. The country is so well organised. They like good functioning in everything”.⁷

As it emerges from his correspondence, Fermi never expressed his opinion on matters that did not strictly concerned physics; it was an unpleasant peculiarity of Fermi. Certainly it was a period in which events of some consideration did not lack both in Italy and in Germany!⁸

During approximately the three years from the end of university and the formulation of his statistics theory, Fermi’s work can be divided into four phases.

Göttingen (January 1923-August 1923)

In these eight months, Fermi went to Göttingen on a scholarship assigned him on 4 November 1922 by the Ministry of Education.

The Weimar Republic was undergoing a very bad crisis and although Fermi personally witnessed its economical disaster, still greatly admired the country’s organising ability (cmp. the quoted recollections of Rasetti).⁹ However, there is no trace of these events in Fermi’s letters from Germany. Even more surprising, there isn’t any comment on Göttingen’s scientific environment, except for the quite generic statement: “The professors, especially Born, are nice people and they don’t give it as if it were the Keys of the Kingdom”.¹⁰ Heisenberg, in an interview with T. S. Kuhn of 1963, remembered then that he had met Fermi at that time and that he hadn’t much liked him:

⁶ Until then he was, to all intents and purposes, an autodidact; cmp. SASSI, SEBASTIANI (1999).

⁷ Cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T. S. Kuhn with F. Rasetti and E. Persico, 8 April 1963, p. 12.

⁸ Fermi had this attitude all his life.

⁹ For instance, in November 1923, one dollar was worth some milliards of marks and the exchange rate with Italian money was especially favourable, so that Fermi was able to buy a brand new bicycle, cmp. L. FERMI (1954). The political situation was also tragical and in January 1923, when Fermi arrived at Göttingen, there was the Franco-Belgian occupation of the near Ruhr zone (about 100 km west of Göttingen) as pledge for the German war debts.

¹⁰ “I professori, specialmente Born, sono persone simpatiche e non la fanno cader troppo dall’alto”, cmp. stamped postcard to Persico of 30.1.1923; a photostat is in the AMAL. ARCH. (1E_{bis}/n.c.).

“I had some discussions with Fermi, but it must have been that Fermi was not – I would say – in a good period of his young life. He may have had personal problems; I don’t know what the matter was. He had always been a bit shy and kept by himself, and it was not too easy to get really close to him. Still, I liked him as a rather different type of physicist. [...] in Göttingen we never had a real conversation; we met in the seminar, and occasionally on the streets, but not in that way that we really got in touch”.¹¹

The lack of agreement with the German scientific environment is testified also by other sources.¹² Furthermore, at Göttingen Fermi could be suffering from the so-called ‘swot syndrome’. Fermi, accustomed to be outstanding and considered a very talented youth in Italy, when suddenly in an ‘inter pares’ environment, could have had psychological problems. Anyhow, in this period Born was holding a seminar for a few people, among whom there were Fermi and Heisenberg.¹³ Born seemed to Heisenberg: “as an extremely good mathematician who [...] had not so much feeling about how the things in atomic physics were”. But Fermi, “disliked these mathematical subtleties, proof of convergence and such [...] I mean, Fermi felt, ‘That’s not physics’. [...] Fermi was not so pleased with [this seminar of Born]”.¹⁴

Göttingen’s interest for the new physics was partly due to the great mathematician David Hilbert who in 1912, as Tagliaferri relates,¹⁵ decided that ‘physics was too difficult for physicists’. So he asked Sommerfeld to send him some youths of great merit. Among them there were Heisenberg and Pauli. In a letter to Einstein dated April 7 1923, about three months after Fermi’s

¹¹ Cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T. S. Kuhn with W. Heisenberg, 15 February 1963, p. 14 (We are grateful to D. Cassidy for this information).

¹² “According to Samuel Allison, many years later Fermi remembered that period with some bitterness: the professors of Göttingen considered themselves, in Fermi’s opinion, as omniscients and they didn’t at all care to encourage him”, “Secondo Samuel Allison, molti anni dopo Fermi ricordava quel periodo con una certa amarezza: i professori di Göttinga si consideravano, secondo Fermi, onniscienti e non si preoccupavano certo di incoraggiarlo”, cmp. PONTECORVO (1993), pp. 26-27. When Fermi came back to Italy and met G. Uhlenbeck in the fall of 1923, his disappointment was even more evident: “[Uhlenbeck] found he’d just come back from Germany, completely discouraged. He’d been to Göttingen for a term and had been given the works - on the lines of ‘This guy can’t know anything, he’s small fry, he’s never studied any place where it’s worth studying.’ The man was so thoroughly dejected that he was planning to give up physics. Uhlenbeck advised: ‘Don’t do that before you’ve had a talk with Ehrenfest. Go and see him’.”, cmp. GOUDSMIT (1972). However, the idea of a Fermi intentioned to give up physics is surely exaggerated.

¹³ Those present at the seminar were: Heisenberg, Jordan, Fermi, probably Hund, and at most another couple of persons.

¹⁴ Cmp. the mentioned interview with Heisenberg, p. 6.

¹⁵ Cmp. TAGLIAFERRI (1985), note 92, p. 336.

arrival at Göttingen, Born wrote about Heisenberg's qualities and their regret for the state of quantum physics,¹⁶ also mentioned in several previous Heisenberg's letters to Pauli.¹⁷

If these were Born and Heisenberg's worries, the following assertion by Segrè, concerning the beginning of 1923 at Göttingen, sounds quite unlikely: "[...] an extremely important incubation period prelude to the flowering of the new quantum mechanics that just in Göttingen had in this period one of the most important centres".¹⁸ The impression is, instead, of a widespread disappointment and, as Tagliaferri objects: "[...] this is an unjustified inference: in 1923 the new mechanics could be a desire but it wasn't known – either in Göttingen or elsewhere – which way to follow to achieve it".¹⁹

Fermi was not discouraged and worked hard, also not to disappoint friends' expectations in his sojourn in Göttingen.²⁰

In February 1923, only one month after his arrival, Fermi prepared a work

¹⁶ "[...] I worked a lot and kept a good number of pupils busy. However, the problems faced are small: in spite of all efforts, I'm not able to penetrate the big quantum enigmas", "[...] ho lavorato parecchio e ho fatto anche lavorare un buon numero di allievi. Ma i problemi affrontati sono soltanto piccoli problemi: nonostante ogni sforzo, non riesco a penetrare i grandi enigmi dei quanti", cmp. Born (1973²), p. 89. When Fermi arrived at Göttingen, the two most renowned Born's collaborators were taking turns. In fact Pauli, Born's assistant until the spring of 1922, went to Copenhagen as Bohr's assistant from October 1922 to September 1923, and Heisenberg was to replace him, cmp. for example TAGLIAFERRI (1985), p. 316.

¹⁷ As a matter of fact, on 19 February 1923 writing to Pauli about the work conducted with Born, Heisenberg asserts: "[...] to summarise it all: 'it's a torture'", "[...] um alles kurz zusammenzufassen: 'es ist ein Jammer'", cmp. PAULI (1979), p. 80. Two days after, always writing to Pauli, Heisenberg ironically states: "[...] a theory can always still be wrong, if it produces something right, but can *never* be right if it produces something wrong", "Eine Theorie kann immer noch falsch sein, wenn sie etwas richtiges ergibt, aber sie kann *nie* richtig sein, wenn sie etwas falsches ergibt", cmp. PAULI (1979), p. 82. And, on 26 March of the same year, Heisenberg closed a letter to Pauli saying: "[...] we [Heisenberg and Born] don't want to get uselessly tired. Basically we are convinced that all helium models proposed until now are false as the whole atomic physics. We hope that this wonderful spring [...] would change all, but really all", "Aber wir wollen uns nicht unnötig streiten. Im Grunde sind wir beide der Überzeugung, daß alle bisherigen He-Modelle ebenso falsch sind, wie die ganze Atomphysik. Hoffen wir, daß der jetzige prachtvolle Frühling [...] alles, alles wendet", cmp. PAULI (1979), p. 86.

¹⁸ "[...] un periodo estremamente importante di incubazione preludente allo sboccio della nuova meccanica quantistica, che appunto in Göttingen aveva in quegli anni uno dei centri maggiori", cmp. F.N.M., p. XXVI.

¹⁹ "[...] quest'illusione è ingiustificata: nel 1923 la nuova meccanica poteva essere un'aspirazione, ma non si sapeva – né a Göttinga né altrove – che strada prendere per realizzarla", cmp. TAGLIAFERRI (1985), p. 351, note 4.

²⁰ Persico, besides waiting for scientific news from what he calls "quantum land" ("paese dei quanti", cmp. AMAL. ARCH. (1E_{bis}/n.c)), when Fermi is about to return in Italy, writes to him: "And we hope that you'll bring us some Göttingen's air bottles to renew our scientific environment and guide us on a serious and organised work", "E speriamo che ci porterai alcune bombole di aria gottinghese, per rinnovare i nostri ambienti scientifici e guidarci ad un lavoro organizzato e serio", cmp. copy of the 23.06.1923 stamped postcard, *ibid.*

that would be later published on the *Nuovo Cimento*: *The adiabatic principle and systems that don't admit angular coordinates*²¹ (F.N.M.12).

After nearly two months, namely in April 1923, Fermi completed a second work that he considered important. Following the rules he had given to himself,²² he published it on the *Physikalische Zeitschrift*: *Proof that a normal mechanical system is usually quasi-ergodish*²³ (F.N.M.11a).

As Segrè stated in the F.N.M. introduction: “[...] Prof. Ehrenfest, who had delved deeply into the foundations of statistical mechanics, was impressed by the paper. He gave to Uhlenbeck, who was going to Rome for a while, a letter for Fermi with a number of questions and in this way Uhlenbeck met Fermi for the first time in the fall of 1924 [sic]”. Actually things went differently, as the meeting between the two physicists took place one year before, namely in the autumn of 1923.²⁴ It's worth noting that Ehrenfest was struck by this article which he later quoted in an analytic mechanics article arrived at the *Zeitschrift für Physik* on 2 October 1923.²⁵

The third work published by Fermi at Göttingen is: *Some theorems of analytical mechanics that are important for quantum theory*²⁶ (F.N.M.13) and dates back to April 1923. The same date of the previous article.²⁷

On 16 April 1923 Fermi wrote to Persico: “I'm working hard on a border work among celestial mechanics, statistical mechanics and quantum theory. But I can't foresee where I'll be driven at”.²⁸ In addition, on the 21st of April

²¹ *Il principio delle adiabatiche ed i sistemi che non ammettono coordinate angolari*, *Nuovo Cimento*, 25 (1923), 171-175.

²² Fermi, well aware of the Italian scientific isolation, published his most important works on foreign reviews, cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 35.

²³ *Beweis, dass ein mechanisches normalsystem im allgemeinen quasi-ergodisch ist*, *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, 24 (1923), 261-265.

²⁴ The spreading of the error, that involved Segrè and others, presumably originated with the book by Fermi's wife; cmp. L. Fermi (1954). In the fall of 1924 Fermi was in Leyden, Holland. After all, Uhlenbeck refers that: “[...] in 1923 I also met and became good friends with Enrico Fermi”, cmp. UHLENBECK (1976), p. 45.

²⁵ Cmp. EHRENFEST (1923). It seems that Ehrenfest used with Uhlenbeck the following expression: “[...] ‘I've seen an article by a young fellow and it looks pretty good; you should look him up’”, cmp. GOUDSMIT (1972), p. 83.

²⁶ *Alcuni teoremi di meccanica analitica importanti per la teoria dei quanti*, *Nuovo Cimento*, 25 (1923), 271-285.

²⁷ There arose the issue of the time order of the works, cleared up in the fifth note: “[...] the writer has recently demonstrated that normal mechanical systems are generally quasi ergodish”, “[...] chi scrive ha recentemente dimostrato che i sistemi meccanici normali sono in generale quasi-ergodici”, cmp. F.N.M., p. 93.

²⁸ “Io sto molto lavorando ad un lavoro di confine fra la meccanica celeste, la meccanica statistica e la teoria quantistica. Ma non posso ancora prevedere dove andrò a sbattere”, cmp. stamped postcard to Persico of 16.04.1923. A photostat is conserved by AMAL. ARCH. (1E_{bis}/n.c.).

he specified to his friend: “[...] I have three rather important publications ready [...]”.²⁹

Rome (September 1923-August 1924)

In September 1923 Fermi came back home from Germany. On his arrival he found a country grieved by fascist violence. It was more than ever necessary for Fermi to find a job. With Corbino’s help, he was assigned with teaching mathematics to chemistry students for the academical year 1923-24 in Rome.³⁰

In the autumn of 1923 Fermi met Uhlenbeck and, as already mentioned, the latter was deeply impressed by Fermi’s disappointment about his stay in Göttingen.³¹ On 29 October 1923 the board of examiners assigned the fellowship to Fermi for the second consecutive year.³² However, since Fermi had already taken advantage of one fellowship: “[...] it would not be possible, as laid down in article 157 of the current university regulations, to assign it to him a second time”.³³ In spite of this the board of examiners, on account of “[...] the exceptional value of dr. Fermi”³⁴ in a departure from regulations, expressed itself favourably on a second fellowship assignment. As a matter of fact, Fermi remained in Italy until September 1924, when he went to Leyden on a fellowship grant by the Rockefeller foundation.

²⁹ Cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 204. Probably the work Fermi refers to in the letter of the 16th it’s inclusive of those mentioned in the letter of the 21st of April.

³⁰ Cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 34.

³¹ Perhaps it’s worth noting that Uhlenbeck’s recollections could have been distorted, and perhaps ‘projected’ on Fermi, by the identity crisis the Dutch physicist was going through. In fact, when in Rome, he was devoting himself to a career of professional historian: “[...] still, even his [Fermi’s] influence did not turn my back to physics. I suppose I went through what nowadays is called an identity crisis. Anyway, when I came back in June 1925, I thought that my real interest was in the study of cultural history, and that perhaps I should forget about physics”, cmp. UHLENBECK (1976), p. 45.

³² As in the previous year, Fermi in 1923-24, competed both for a scholarship abroad and for an internal one. The board of examiners stated: “Mighty and fertile is the activity of this young candidate of absolutely exceptional value and the Committee expresses the vow that to him will be given the possibility to widen the field of his knowledge in the interest of the Italian science. [...] The Committee therefore, declares Fermi Enrico winner of the scholarship abroad”, “Poderosa e feconda è l’attività di questo giovane concorrente di valore assolutamente eccezionale e la Commissione formula il voto che a lui sia dato modo di allargare sempre più il campo delle sue conoscenze nell’interesse della scienza italiana. [...] La Commissione pertanto dichiara vincitore dell’assegno di perfezionamento all’estero il dott. Fermi Enrico”, cmp. “Bollettino Ufficiale, Atti di Amministrazione”, Ministero della Pubblica Istruzione, 27 March (1924), year 51, no.13, pp. 714-719.

³³ “[...] non sarà possibile, a norma dell’articolo 157 del vigente regolamento generale universitario, assegnargliela una seconda volta”

³⁴ “[...] valore eccezionale del dott. Fermi”.

Fermi's didactical activity did not affect his scientific production. In fact, in December 1923 - January 1924 he prepared three very important works (F.N.M.16, F.N.M. 19 and F.N.M.17a). Two (F.N.M. 16 e 19) are fundamental to understand the evolution towards the new quantum statistics and will be considered later. The third can be defined his first article on quantum³⁵ and was presented on 16 December 1923 by Corbino at the Lincei, as a short essay titled: *On the probability of quantum states*.³⁶ In this work Fermi deals originally with a delicate quantum problem that later attracted major attention.³⁷ The work, that Fermi considered quite important, appeared also in a German version on the *Zeitschrift für Physik* (F.N.M.17b)³⁸ and was quoted by Planck in June 1924.³⁹ The German version has a 'post quem' limit, defined in February 1924;⁴⁰ in this version Fermi thanks Born for his advice concerning an imprecision in the previous Italian version. This is indirect evidence of a correspondence between Born and Fermi, immediately after his return from Germany. In the Amaldi archive is kept the typewritten version that Fermi sent to the editor of the *Zeitschrift für Physik*. Above the title a note says: "Corrections to Mr. Prof. Dr. M. Born, Göttingen, Planckstrasse 21".⁴¹ A few months later Fermi made use⁴² of the results obtained to deal with some astrophysical topics that M. N. Saha had proposed in 1921.

In the summer of 1924 the political situation in Italy was very similar to that of summer 1922. The Matteotti murder on 10 June 1924 shook the fascist regime, saved by the indifference of the Italian democratic forces. Thanks to an unpublished letter⁴³ it's possible to infer that Fermi, already before the summer vacations of 1924 he spent at Moena on the Dolomites, started to draw up what was later called the 'virtual quantum method'.⁴⁴ This

³⁵ The work on Richardson's statistical theory still constituted after all a classical attempt to study the photoelectric effect. That was a problem more simply and effectively tackled with the introduction of light quanta as Einstein did in 1905, even if the scientific community refused such an innovative approach.

³⁶ *Sulla probabilità degli stati quantici*, Rendiconti Lincei, 32 (1923), 493-495.

³⁷ In BRILLOUIN (1930), find an in-depth comparison of different treatments on the subject.

³⁸ *Über die Wahrscheinlichkeit der Quantenzustände*, *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 26 (1924), 54-56.

³⁹ Cmp. PLANCK (1924).

⁴⁰ That's a consequence of the fact that in F.N.M.20 (of February 1924), Fermi still uses the results he found in F.N.M.17a and not those, slightly different, he reached in F.N.M.17b.

⁴¹ "Korrektur an Hrrn. Prof. Dr. M. Born, Göttingen, Planckstrasse 21", cmp. AMAL. ARCH. (446/n.c.). That is a proof of Born's direct interest in Fermi. Note the odd coincidence of street names!

⁴² Cmp. *Nuovo Cimento*, 1 (1924), 153-158.

⁴³ Letter to Persico dated Varese 19.VIII.'24, cmp. AMAL. ARCH. (1E_{bis}/n.c.).

⁴⁴ It's important to note that there are many other denominations for the virtual quantum method: collision theory, impact theory, equivalent photon method, Weizsäcker-Williams' method.

article appeared on the *Zeitschrift für Physik* as: *On the collision theory between atoms and electrical charged particles*⁴⁵ (F.N.M.23b). This work can be considered as one of the most significant Fermi's contributions before the discovery of quantum statistics. It is based on a simple, efficient idea that uses analogy as a scientific method: utilize consolidated results in a specific area of physics to solve an apparently distant problem.⁴⁶

Leyden (September 1924-December 1924)

From September to December 1924, Fermi stayed at Leyden on another *fellowship grant* by the International Education Board, founded by J. D. Rockefeller. V. Volterra, with the precious help of H. A. Lorentz and W. Rose (President of the Foundation), did his best for Fermi's stay in Holland. In two letters, Rose showed his interest for Fermi's case.⁴⁷

From the correspondence with Persico it's possible to reconstruct Fermi's journey,⁴⁸ arriving at Leyden, by sea, on 12 September 1924. This second period of study abroad was, as for human relations, much more congenial to Fermi. This is evident from a letter dated 27 October 1924 to his sister Maria.⁴⁹ In Leyden Fermi made acquaintance, besides Ehrenfest, Einstein, Keesom, Lorentz, with some young physicists as G. Dicke, S. Goudsmit, R. de L. Kronig, J. Tinbergen.

⁴⁵ *Über die Theorie des Stosses zwischen Atomen und elektrisch geladenen Teilchen*, *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 29 (1924), 315-327. An Italian version appeared also on the *Nuovo Cimento* (F.N.M.23a): *Sulla teoria dell'urto tra atomi e corpuscoli elettrici*, *Nuovo Cimento*, 2 (1925), 143-158.

⁴⁶ The application of this method, here called 'analogy method', will be the keystone for the formulation of Fermi's quantum statistic.

⁴⁷ Cmp. VOLT. ARCH. (20/518). It results that Fermi was given a \$350 check for a period of three months at Leyden. Initially Fermi should stay six months (this reduction of period was a rule except for the foundation). We are grateful to M. De Maria for this information.

⁴⁸ Cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), pp. 205, 206. The correspondence recently emerged shows how Fermi, on 26 August 1924, was still in Moena on the Dolomites. Persico sent him the passport he needed for the Netherlands.

⁴⁹ "Leyden 27.10.1924.[...] I always feel good and, amongst big and small, I make a discovery every twenty days on the average [...] everybody holds me in deep respect [...] Einstein left the past week making me enthusiastic sympathy declarations [...] Among my new acquaintances: prof. Ehrenfest is a very nice person, even though he wouldn't look too bad in a second-hand clothing shop in the ghetto; he takes very good care of the school and his pupils, and he has a special quality to get hold of those from whom one can expect good results for the future. I then met naturally many young ones [...]", "Leyden 27.10.1924.[...] mi trovo sempre bene e, tra grandi e piccole, faccio in media una scoperta ogni venti giorni [...] tutti hanno un profondo rispetto di me [...]. Einstein è partito la settimana scorsa, facendomi entusiastiche dichiarazioni di simpatia [...] Tra i miei nuovi conoscenti: il prof. Ehrenfest è una persona molto simpatica, benché non sfigurerebbe affatto in un negozio di abiti usati in ghetto; si occupa moltissimo della scuola e dei suoi studenti, ed ha una speciale abilità nel saper pescare fin dai primi anni quelli dai quali si possono sperare dei buoni risultati per l'avvenire. Ho conosciuto poi naturalmente molti giovani [...]", cmp. E. VINASSA DE REGNY (1992).

Ehrenfest, together with Lorentz, was the most important person in Leyden and much of his time was devoted to teaching and forming his young pupils (he was really a talent-scout).⁵⁰

In Leyden Fermi became part of an ‘horizontal’ vision of the teacher-student relation. On the contrary, Göttingen’s was structured more ‘vertically’.

During the Dutch period (unlike the German), Fermi made many new “discoveries” without yet completing one single article. There were many topics to write about, but writing an article would have needed a time that Fermi, at Leyden, preferred to employ otherwise.

In conclusion it can be said that the major advantage obtained by Fermi during the three months spent at Leyden, wasn’t just the widening of his technical knowledge, but mainly the opportunity to collaborate with other physicists. Ehrenfest in fact, as good a teacher as he was, understood very well the psychological frustration of a pupil facing too hazy physical issues.⁵¹

On the contrary Born, at Göttingen, did not worry over such issues. As David Cassidy states, he had a totally different attitude: “[...] the shy and retiring theorist, plagued by hypochondria [...] the bashful Born seemed overwhelmed by the numbers of students flocking to Göttingen”.⁵² In a letter to Einstein dated 30 April 1922, Born writes: “[...] it’s just about to start the wretched semester, true ‘perturbation’ of meditative work”.⁵³

Ehrenfest was instead very happy to work with students. He was a great teacher, thanks to his great knowledge of physics and his extremely collaborative and open attitude. Such a milieu was ideal for Fermi, very pleased to work with people more akin to his scientific style, less mathematical and more physical, like Ehrenfest. Naturally Ehrenfest soon noticed Fermi’s tal-

⁵⁰ Some hand-written drafts of Ehrenfest, dating spring 1926 or 1927 following the visit of an English-American group of students, read (note Fermi’s name among the “leading students”): “[...] for not being a Dutchman I can freely express my great admiration for Dutch science and Dutch scientists [...] you get the chance of > 1/Million to get the Nobel-Prize in your life-time if you only arrange to be born as a Dutchman (Density for Leiden !) [...] Leading students (Fermi, Breit, Kronig, Gibbson) [...] small numbers, atmosphere of play (Einstein !!!) [...] not hasty, steadiness, perseverance, enormous quiet, pressing energy, big reserves of times for exigency [...] an organism not a machinery, just as science in Holland”, cmp. A.H.Q.P. (60/...).

⁵¹ In a beautiful letter of January 1924, Ehrenfest talked about the young Americans he had met in America: “[...] The young [here in America] is terribly sound – hygiene, sport, school education as easy as winking until 23 years old, so that not even a soul is tickled by the devil”, “[...] Die Jugend ist beängstigend gesund - Hygiene, Sport, strand-einfacher Schuldrill bis 23 sorgt, dass keine Seele vom Teufel gekitzelt wird”, cmp. A.H.Q.P. (60/2).

⁵² Cmp. CASSIDY (1992), p. 138. Quotation reported as in BELLONI (1994), notes 39-40.

⁵³ “[...] sta per ricominciare il benedetto semestre, vera ‘perturbazione’ del lavoro contemplativo”, cmp. BORN (1973²), p. 83.

ent and there is evidence that they analyzed together Frenkel's work on electroconduction in metals.⁵⁴ Moreover, it would be interesting to verify if Fermi found out about the Bose-Einstein statistics through Ehrenfest or, at any rate, during his stay in Holland.⁵⁵

Florence (January 1925-December 1925)

In December 1924 Fermi, just back from Leyden, went to Florence as lecturer of theoretical mechanics and electromagnetism with an annual appointment.⁵⁶ Conscientiously, he had started to prepare the lectures and the course two months before in Leyden. The Florence Physics Institute was located in Arcetri, and was directed by the physicist and Senator A. Garbasso, also Florence's mayor. Rasetti had also been there since November 1922.⁵⁷

In December 1924, in Florence, Fermi completed two works. One had been started at Leyden in the previous October. However, it can be said that both these works and some others that followed, were carried out mostly to increase the number of his publications for university teaching qualifications (obtained on 2 March 1925). Among them we remember an experimental work conducted together with his friend Rasetti, from January 1925 to May 1925.

Thanks to Rasetti, in fact, Fermi got to know some works by Wood, Ellet, and Hanle⁵⁸ concerning the weak effects of magnetic fields on the polarisation of mercury resonance radiation. From Fermi-Kronig's correspondence in the A.H.Q.P., it's possible to reconstruct the evolution of Fermi's interest (initially a bit different). The influence of a work by Bohr on the same subject is also evident.⁵⁹ It's important to observe that this work represented Fermi's second attempt in experimental physics after several years of theo-

⁵⁴ Cmp. EHRENFEST-JOFFÉ (1990), letter no. 77 on 24 November 1924: "Here when we inspected Frenkel's work on metals electroconduction [Zeitschrift für Physik, 24 (1924), 214-240] I convinced myself, even more than before, that in this work there are many ingenious ideas but also an enormous confusion. There are not only heavenly ways but also earthly ones. Perhaps me and E. Fermi (Professor in Florence, now here), that appraised the sharpness of this work, we'll find the right way and put a stop to the enormous confusion". We are grateful to R. Pisegna and to T. Jakobson for the translation from Russian.

⁵⁵ The second paragraph of EHRENFEST'S (1925) contains his first note on the Bose-Einstein statistics.

⁵⁶ Cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 37.

⁵⁷ Rasetti remembers that, in this period: "[...] we were very close. We practically lived together", cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T.S. Kuhn with F. Rasetti and E. Persico, 8 April 1963, p. 12.

⁵⁸ Cmp. F.N.M. for bibliographical indications.

⁵⁹ Fermi-Kronig's correspondence is contained in A.H.Q.P. (16/4).

retical work. The first experimental contribution dated back to 1922 and was a part of the thesis on *Image formation with Röntgen rays*. The idea to use a radiofrequency field to conduct experimental research on atomic spectra was forerunner of a number of subsequent applications. It is probably for this idea that this contribution is to be appreciated.

The physicists Fermi came into contact with at Leyden exerted a positive influence on him. He kept in touch with the Dutch scientific environment also after his return to Italy, and Kronig can be considered to all intents and purposes as the link, during 1925, between Fermi and the other European physicists.

Kronig and Fermi met at Leyden and after Fermi's return to Italy there was a considerable exchange of letters between the two young physicists, less frequent after 1926. Travelling a lot and meeting many people, Kronig updated Fermi on what was going on in Berlin, Copenhagen, Göttingen, Leyden and Munich. Furthermore, Kronig spent with Fermi the August 1925 summer vacations in S. Vito di Cadore⁶⁰. Probably that was the occasion for Fermi to discuss for the first time the new-born quantum mechanics. It's important to observe that Heisenberg, on 5 June 1925 (about two months before his famous article), wrote Kronig a letter where the non-commutative multiplication rule first appeared.⁶¹ Also Pauli, in that period, kept in close touch with Kronig.

Fermi's quantum statistics

As it is known, Fermi or Fermi-Dirac statistics is the second quantum statistics proposed shortly after Bose-Einstein's in 1924-1925. Dirac recalls: "I worked out the basic relations for this new statistics, and I published this work. Soon after publication I got a letter from Fermi pointing out that this statistics was not really a new one; he had proposed it some time earlier [...] When I looked through Fermi's paper, I remembered that I had seen it previously, but I had completely forgotten it [...] At the time that I read Fermi's paper, I did not see how it could be important for any of the basic problems of quantum theory; it was so much a detached piece of work. It had com-

⁶⁰ Amaldi witnessed the meeting with Kronig: "Fermi was very young; he was 23 or 24 years old. A friend of his had come to the same place. That was R. de L. Kronig. [...] Kronig was a great friend of Fermi. They met when Fermi had been in the Netherlands to work with Ehrenfest. [...]", cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by C. Weiner with E. Amaldi, 9 and 10 April 1969, p. 1.

⁶¹ Cmp. VAN DER WAERDEN (1967) and CASSIDY (1992).

pletely slipped out of my mind, and when I wrote up my work on the anti-symmetrical wave functions, I had no recollection of it at all".⁶²

The two physicists arrived independently to the formulation of their quantum statistics, following very different approaches that, although both based on classical physics, differed greatly from⁶³ the drastic positions of Göttingen and Copenhagen schools. Dirac's work⁶⁴ was presented to the Royal Society on 26 August 1926. That was more than six months after the Italian version by Fermi (F.N.M.30)⁶⁵ and more than three months after the more detailed German version (F.N.M.31).⁶⁶

In Fermi's case, two other previous contributions anticipated the conclusive article of 1926. The first one is a memoir presented to the Lincei in December 1923: *On Stern's theory of absolute entropy constant of a perfect monatomic gas* (F.N.M.16).⁶⁷ The second significant contribution is an article Fermi wrote in January 1924, later published on the *Nuovo Cimento: Considerations on the quantization of systems containing identical elements* (F.N.M.19).⁶⁸

Therefore, both the mentioned precursory works (on thermodynamical-

⁶² Cmp. DIRAC (1977), p. 133. The short Fermi's letter, somewhat angry, to which Dirac refers is dated Rome 25 October 1926 and is fully reported here: "Mr. P.A.M. Dirac, St. John's College, Cambridge. Dear Sir! In your interesting [sic] paper "On the theory of Quantum Mechanics" (Proc. Roy. Soc. 112, 661, 1926) you have put forward a theory of the Ideal Gas based on Pauli's exclusion Principle. Now a theory of the ideal gas that is practically identical to yours was published by me at the beginning of 1926 (Zs. f. Phys, 36, p. 902; Lincei Rend. February 1926). Since I suppose that you have not seen my paper, I beg to attract your attention on it. I am, Sir, Yours Truly Enrico Fermi", cmp. A.H.Q.P. (59/2).

⁶³ About Dirac: "he struggled to construct the new QM as a *generalization* of (and not as a *break* with) classical physics, through a systematic utilisation of the classical Hamiltonian formalism", cmp. DE MARIA, LA TEANA (1983), p. 596. In a letter to Persico of 23 September 1925, he says of Fermi: "My impression is that during the past few months there has not been much progress, in spite of the formal results on the zoology of spectroscopic terms achieved by Heisenberg. For my taste, they have begun to exaggerate their tendency to give up understanding things", cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 209. Dirac remembers his own impressions of the period: "I was so impressed then with the Hamiltonian formalism as the basis of atomic physics, that I thought anything not connected with it would not be much good. I thought there was not much in it [Heisenberg's paper] and I put it aside for a week or so", reported by MEHRA in SALAM, WIGNER (1972), p. 31.

⁶⁴ Cmp. DIRAC (1926). Previously Dirac, in an article that was not published, showed interest for the new developments of the Bose-Einstein new quantum statistics, cmp. MEHRA, RECHENBERG (1982), p. 109.

⁶⁵ This first formulation was presented (as a memoir) by Garbasso to Lincei on 7 February 1926: *On the quantization of the monatomic perfect gas*, (F.N.M.30), cmp. Rend. Lincei, 3 (1926), 145-149.

⁶⁶ This version, larger than the previous, appeared on 11 May 1926 on the *Zeitschrift für Physik* (F.N.M.31), cmp. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 36 (1926), 902-912. Later on, unless different indications, one will always refer to this work.

⁶⁷ *Sopra la teoria di Stern della costante assoluta dell'entropia di un gas perfetto monoatomico*, Rendiconti Lincei, 32 (II) (1923), 395-398.

⁶⁸ *Considerazioni sulla quantizzazione dei sistemi che contengono degli elementi identici*, *Nuovo Cimento*, 1 (1924), 145-152.

statistical topics), can be set in the Italian ‘intermezzo’ of Fermi, between the German and Dutch period.

The ‘Leitmotiv’ that ideally links these three works (F.N.M.16, 19, 31) is the Sackur and Tetrode formula for the entropy absolute constant of an ideal monatomic gas:

$$S_0 = \frac{5}{2}R + R \ln \left[\left(\frac{2\pi m}{h^2} \right)^{\frac{5}{2}} k^{\frac{5}{2}} \right]$$

This result, obtained thanks to many scientists’ efforts at the beginning of the century⁶⁹, represented for Fermi a guide on the way towards the discovery of his quantum statistics.⁷⁰

In his article of 1923 (F.N.M.16), Fermi seems to be already favourably impressed by Stern’s derivation⁷¹ of the entropy constant. This interest continued also afterwards.⁷² It is natural to wonder how Fermi became interested in Stern’s method and, more generally, in entropy constant.

One possible hypothesis is tightly connected with the Göttingen stay. In August 1923 Born published a very long article (nearly 250 pages) on the properties of solids: *Atomic theory of the solid state (dynamics of the crystal lattices)*.⁷³ In chapter 35, Born defined Stern’s method. He followed almost

⁶⁹ For an excellent storiographical reconstruction, cmp. DESALVO (1992).

⁷⁰ Actually, Dirac’s approach was based solely on the study of symmetry properties of a wave function in a system of many particles in the new ondulatory mechanics. It can be said, in fact, that Fermi’s work is the last important thermodynamical statistical work written in the language of old quantum physics, whereas Dirac’s is the first important statistical result obtained by new quantum mechanics.

⁷¹ Cmp. STERN (1913) and Stern (1919). Although Stern arrived at the same formula of Sackur and Tetrode, he adopted a very different method. In 1913 he had the brilliant idea to carry out the calculus twice to find the equilibrium pressure of vapour, between solid and vapour phases. The calculus was carried out by Stern first thermodynamically and then with a kinetic model. With the thermodynamical calculus, extrapolating the high temperature limit, Stern obtained an expression containing the entropy constant S_0 for the pressure of vapour. As for kinetic calculus, it was valid only at high temperatures, and vapour pressure was obtainable without undetermined constants. Comparing the two expressions, Stern was then able to determinate the value of S_0 , reaching exactly the formula Sackur and Tetrode had found the previous year. In 1919 Stern returned on the subject, accepting part of TETRODE’s method (1915).

⁷² In fact a rich paragraph of his 1934 book *Molecole e Cristalli*, is dedicated to this subject, cmp. FERMI (1966)_a, par. 8-2. He dealt with this subject also in the 1951-52 *Notes on Thermodynamics and Statistics*, cmp. FERMI (1966)_b, par. 49.

⁷³ Cmp. BORN (1923), pp. 701-709. For more information see CORDELLA, SEBASTIANI (1999)_d, (2000)_{a,b}. For what concerns Sackur and Tetrode’s works, in his article Born writes (almost exactly as Stern did in 1919) rather pessimistically: “[...] In this derivation there is a lot of arbitrariness, especially for the introduction of atoms number N”, “[...] Bei dieser Ableitung bleibt vieles willkürlich, vor allem die Einführung der Atomzahl N”. Born is much more enthusiastic of Stern’s method: “[...] Through

exactly Stern's 1919 second formulation. Significantly, Born completed this work just when Fermi was in Göttingen.⁷⁴ Born used to have his own work checked by collaborators who liked finding mistakes or making suggestions. In 1921 E. Brody⁷⁵ was especially concerned with entropy constant. He was of great help to Born in preparing the review on solids.⁷⁶ As showed in the previous paragraph, in Germany Fermi was busy with analytical dynamics until April 1923. From this time on, there is no trace of Fermi's scientific interest. However, in F.N.M.19 Fermi made a clear reference to Brody's work of 1921. Moreover, in Göttingen in the same period, Enskog and Nordheim were working at the additivity entropy problem.⁷⁷ So it is quite likely that Fermi found, in the last four months in Göttingen, the right environment to deal with this subject.

F.N.M.16 was presented by Corbino to the Lincei on 2 December 1923. It is a short work of 3 pages and as many paragraphs. In the first two, Fermi refers briefly to the works of SACKUR (1913) TETRODE (1912) and STERN (1913), (1919). Fermi shows appreciation for Stern's method and asserts that the necessity to quantize the phase space of gas, as stated by Sackur and Tetrode, appeared to him unnecessary.⁷⁸

Stern's deduction, on the basis of Nernst's theorem, it is possible to define the only value of the chemical constant, that is the entropy constant of the gas, referred to the condensed phase at the absolute zero", "[...] Bei der sicherlich einwandfreien Ableitung von Stern kommt auch dem Einzelwerte der chemischen Konstanten auf Grund des Nernstschen Theorems ein Sinn zu, nämlich als die Entropiekonstante des Gases, bezogen auf das Kondensat beim absolutem Nullpunkt".

⁷⁴ From Born's letters to Einstein, reported in BORN (1973²), one can understand the effort that Born devoted to this work.

⁷⁵ Brody was an Hungarian physicists facing serious economic difficulties. The main reason is that, for those living on a fixed salary, as Brody, the inflation of the paper-mark was extremely heavy. Moreover, at that time it was not easy to carve out a career for an Hungarian Jewish in Germany. Cmp. BORN (1973²), p. 81.

⁷⁶ In the introduction Born writes: "[...] The more valuable help was given to me by prof. E. Brody; not only he contributed to gather the literature and elaborating some parts, but also provided, mainly through his sharp remarks, to clarify many relations and developing new methods. I'd like to thank him before everybody. Also some of my students helped me with the elaboration of texts and with corrections, especially Mr. P. Jordan, whom I thank for his many valuable comments, and Mr. K. Hermann, G. Heckmann and H. Kornfeld", "[...] Die wertvollste Hilfe bei der Arbeit fand ich durch Herrn Prof. E. Brody; er hat nicht nur zur Sammlung der Literatur beigetragen und manche Abschnitte ausgearbeitet, sondern vor allem durch scharf sinnige Bemerkungen die Klärung vieler Zusammenhänge herbeigeführt und neue Methoden entwickelt. Ihm gebührt an erster Stelle mein Dank. Auch einige meiner Schüler haben mir bei der Ausarbeitung des Textes und dem Lesen der Korrekturen in freundlicher Weise geholfen, vor allem Herr P. Jordan, dem ich viele wertvolle winke verdanke, und die Herren K. Hermann, G. Heckmann und H. Kornfeld", cmp. BORN (1923), pp. V and VI.

⁷⁷ Cmp. DESALVO (1992), p. 512.

⁷⁸ "[...] That, despite the experimental testing[of Sackur-Tetrode's formula], this method seemed to be unsatisfactory, it's demonstrated by the many theoretical works produced, aiming at finding a better demonstration. Of all these attempts, Stern's is the best [...] His method has the advantage of making

Fermi then devoted himself to eliminate the null point energy hypothesis from previous treatments, as Born in 1923 and Stern did in 1919: “in this work I intend to demonstrate that this unnatural hypothesis is by no means necessary [...]”.⁷⁹

As stated above, in 1921 Brody was concerned with the entropy constant. Since his approach was carefully studied by Fermi, the next paragraph will outline the main features of Brody’s article.

Brody’s article of 1921

Brody’s article of 1921: *On the theoretical determination of the chemical constant of a monatomic gas*,⁸⁰ was very important for its influence on Fermi and its concise and elegant solution to the problem of the entropy constant. As stated by Desalvo: “Brody’s treatment became a standard, at least for most of the people accepting the quantization of translational motion. It represents the closest approach to the correct results in terms of the old quantum theory”.⁸¹ The work is divided into two sections: a first quantistic half (*Quantentheoretischer Teil*) and a second statistics half (*Statistischer Teil*).

In the quantistic part, Brody takes into consideration a punctiform particle of mass m in a cubic box of side l with perfect reflecting walls. He refers to a system of Cartesian coordinates parallel to the sides of the box. The particle is free, supposing the gas perfect, so that its velocity components have a constant modulus. The quantum conditions for the particle periodic motions inside the box are:

$$\oint p_i dx_i = \oint m v_i dx_i = 2m|v_i| \int_0^l dx_i = 2m|v_i|l = n_i h \quad (i = x, y, z).$$

none of the arbitrary hypotheses on the gas that other authors need, such as gas quantization of which the reason is not clear”, “[...] Che nonostante la verifica sperimentale [della formula di Sackur-Tetrode] questo modo di dedurla non sia apparso a molti soddisfacente, è dimostrato dal gran numero di lavori teorici, che furono fatti in seguito, con lo scopo di trovarne una dimostrazione migliore. Di tutti questi tentativi, quello che senza dubbio ha meglio raggiunto il suo scopo è quello di Stern [...] Il suo metodo ha il vantaggio di non fare sopra il gas perfetto nessuna di quelle poco legittime ipotesi, che sono necessarie agli altri Autori, come per esempio quella di una quantizzazione del gas stesso, della quale non si vede chiaramente la ragione”, excerpts from F.N.M.16.

⁷⁹ “[...] in questo lavoro mi propongo di dimostrare che questa ipotesi innaturale non è affatto necessaria [...]”.

⁸⁰ Cmp. BRODY (1921). In note eight of this article, Brody refers that this work appeared in Hungarian as a degree thesis in 1917. The purpose of the work was to eliminate a discrepancy in a previous work of Scherrer dated 1916.

⁸¹ Cmp. DESALVO (1992), p. 506.

Therefore, the kinetic energy of the particle is:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m (v_x^2 + v_y^2 + v_z^2) = \frac{h^2}{8ml^2} (n_x^2 + n_y^2 + n_z^2)$$

that agrees with the value that would be obtained by the solution of Schrödinger's equation for a particle in an infinite potential well.

In the statistics part, Brody suggests a substantially new reasoning. First of all he defines energy and volume as physical quantities describing the macroscopic state of the system. For the microscopic state (and that's the main assumption) instead of the coordinates and moments of the N particles, he takes into consideration the quantum numbers n_{ji} (where $j = 1, \dots, N$ and $i = x, y, z$). In order to calculate the thermodynamic probability W , to be inserted in the Boltzmann's formula $S = k \cdot \ln W$, one has to determine in how many different ways it's possible to choose the n_{ji} microscopic states corresponding to a given macroscopic system determined by E and $l = V^{1/3}$.

Since energy can only take discontinuous values, there can be several other possible systems of values for n_{ji} . That is:

$$E \leq \frac{h^2}{8ml^2} (n_{1x}^2 + n_{1y}^2 + n_{1z}^2 + \dots + n_{Nx}^2 + n_{Ny}^2 + n_{Nz}^2) \leq E + dE.$$

The search for numbers of n_{ji} satisfying this inequality is conducted by Brody assuming the $3N$ values of n_{ji} as the Cartesian coordinates of a point in a $3N$ -dimensional space. To calculate W , Brody introduces, without many justifications, a further division by $N!$ so as not to consider the two microscopic states different, but distinguished only by a permutation of atoms.⁸² Finally Brody obtains, as macroscopic state probability:

$$W = \frac{1}{2^{3N} N!} \frac{dV_{3N}}{dE}$$

where dV_{3N} denotes the $3N$ -dimensional spherical shell whose radius are limited by the energy constraint. As Fermi stated in the article of January 1924 (F.N.M.19), to obtain W , Brody: "[...] is forced to put [...] $dE = 1$, being E

⁸² This procedure, needed to justify the entropy additivity and avoid Gibbs' paradox, caused an animated discussion among Planck, Ehrenfest and Schrödinger. In particular Ehrenfest and Trkal, in their well-known article of 1920, stated: "In the majority of calculations of the chemical constant, a special obscurity remains as to the way in which the "thermodynamic probability" of a gas depends on the number of molecules", cmp. EHRENFEST and TRKAL (1920). The German version of the article appeared in 1921.

an energy, so that the probability is substantially defined as the number of gas quantum states [...] reducing to an energy between E and $E+1$. In this way his probability has the dimensions, instead that of a number, of the inverse of an energy”.⁸³ This remark significantly shows how Fermi had carefully studied this work.

Searching for a lacking principle

As already mentioned, in January 1924 Fermi wrote another thermodynamical-statistical article, later published on the *Nuovo Cimento* (F.N.M.19). A little more than a month after the memoir on his improvement of Stern’s method.

In the introduction, Fermi recalls that Sommerfeld’s quantization rules effectively described the hydrogen atom. On the other hand, they were unsuitable for the description of atoms with many electrons. To justify the need of modifying the quantum rules, for a system containing identical elements, Fermi suggested a simple example. He considered a ring with three electrons placed at the vertex of an equilateral triangle.⁸⁴

Subsequently Fermi considered the perfect gas as a separate system of variables and intended to apply the quantization rules: “[...] making various hypotheses on the way to quantize it (to obtain a finite value for the entropy of an ideal gas it’s necessary to quantize it one way or another, since the classical treatment would always lead us to an infinite value)”.⁸⁵

So let’s consider, following Fermi, a perfect gas formed by N punctiform molecules contained in a vessel of volume V . It’s possible to divide the volume V in many parallelepipedal rectangular cells, each one of sides a , b , c , and vol-

⁸³ “[...] è però costretto a porre [...] $dE = 1$, essendo E una energia, con che la probabilità viene in sostanza a essere da lui definita come il numero degli stati quantici del gas [...] che conducono ad una energia compresa tra E ed $E + 1$, di modo che la sua probabilità viene ad avere le dimensioni, anziché di un numero, dell’inverso di un’energia”

⁸⁴ Considering the electrons as *distinguishable*, it’s clear that one has to rotate the ring by a 2π angle to re-obtain the initial situation. If the electrons were instead *indistinguishable* it would be necessary to rotate the ring only by $2\pi/3$. Therefore, denoting with p the angular momentum of the ring, in the first case Sommerfeld’s quantization rules give $(2\pi)p = nh$, while in the second case $(2\pi)p = 3nh$. This kind of arguments on the indistinguishability concept were inspired to Fermi by two works of Compton and Breit, both quoted in F.N.M.19, cmp. A.H. COMPTON (1923) and G. BREIT (1923).

⁸⁵ “[...] facendo diverse ipotesi sopra il modo di quantizzarlo (per ottenere un valore finito dell’entropia di un gas perfetto è necessario quantizzarlo in un modo o nell’altro, poiché la trattazione classica ci condurrebbe sempre ad un valore infinito)” It’s therefore evident that Fermi changed opinion. In F.N.M.16 he still considered an unsuitable hypothesis: “[...] that of a quantization of the gas of which the reason is not clear”.

ume $V_C = a \cdot b \cdot c$. Fermi assumed that inside every cell there would be the same number of molecules. Therefore, there were many possibilities, because we can imagine the volume V as constituted by: N equal cells with 1 molecule, $N/2$ equal cells with 2 molecules, ..., 1 cell with N molecules. Hence, one has N/x cells with $x = N \cdot V_C / V$ molecules in every cell. Assuming, as Brody did, the Cartesian coordinates parallel to the sides of the cell, the system is clearly a separate variables system. In this way, referring to Brody's results, one arrives to the following expression for the total entropy of the N molecules (we have generalised Fermi's procedure):

$$S = kN \left\{ \frac{5}{2} \ln T - \ln P + \ln \left[\frac{(2\pi m)^{\frac{3}{2}} k^{\frac{5}{2}} e^{\frac{5}{2}}}{h^3} \cdot \frac{x}{e} \right] \right\}$$

where V is supposed to be divided in N/x equal cells, each containing x molecules. So far, Fermi's considerations are quite similar to Brody's. But now, following the latter, it would be necessary to consider a single cell that contains N molecules, that is $x = N$. Then, introducing the very arguable division by $N!$ from the previous expression, it's easy to find exactly the Sackur-Tetrode formula. Yet Fermi doesn't follow this procedure and suggests a new, more subtle reasoning. As a matter of fact, the previous formula was derived assuming a particular distribution of molecules into the cells. Let P_r be the probability of this choice, Fermi asserts that the real entropy of the gas S_r is obtainable taking into consideration a further addend $-k \ln P_r$. This assumption, that Fermi doesn't try to justify thoroughly, has actually the importance of a new thermodynamic definition of probability, namely $S = k \ln(W/P_r)$. In so doing, one would obtain:

$$S_r = kN \left\{ \frac{5}{2} \ln T - \ln P + \ln \left[\frac{(2\pi m)^{\frac{3}{2}} k^{\frac{5}{2}} e^{\frac{5}{2}}}{h^3} \right] + \ln(x!)^{\frac{1}{x}} \right\}$$

Therefore, it's evident that the agreement with the Sackur-Tetrode's formula is reached only with $x = 1$. In conclusion, following Fermi's reasoning, the experimental testing of the Sackur-Tetrode formula requires the following. The vessel must be divided into equal N cells of volume V/N , each containing only one molecule, as it was supposed by Sackur in 1913. Of course, the 'ad hoc' character of this hypothesis is evident, but all other ways are to be excluded in the light of experimental facts. In his 1926 article on quantum statistics (where F.N.M.19 is quoted) Fermi would assert: "[...] you

obtain a degeneracy of an expected order of magnitude only if you pick a vessel of so small dimensions that it generally contains only one molecule”.⁸⁶

Further on in the 1924 article, Fermi points out that the discrepancies between S and S_r , arise precisely from the identity of two or more molecules contained in a single cell. In the case of missing identity (for example if many particles in a single cell are of different species), Fermi shows how S would provide, in this case, a correct result for the entropy.

Pursuing this line of thought, Pauli’s exclusion principle can be reached in a roundabout way. Applying Fermi’s analogy method, we can identify, for example, the helium atom with a cell into which two electrons are disposed. In that case, the previous topics suggest that there must be lack of a principle affirming that it’s impossible to find both the electrons with the same quantum numbers.⁸⁷ This “organizing” principle is obviously Pauli’s exclusion principle, but not in Pauli’s originally formulation. In fact, following Fermi, thanks to what we called here the analogy method, this result can be extended to a lot of situations (collection of quantum harmonic oscillators, etc.).

Rasetti recalls that: “[Fermi] told much later to Segrè that the division of phase space into finite cells had occupied him very much and that had not Pauli discovered the exclusion principle he might have arrived at it in a roundabout way from the entropy constant”.⁸⁸

“Ante/post-quem” limits of Fermi’s statistics

Fermi’s article on new quantum statistics⁸⁹ was presented by Garbasso to the Lincei, in a condensed form, on 7 February 1926 (F.N.M.30), a little more than two years after F.N.M.19. On 26 March 1926, the *Zeitschrift für Physik* received a more detailed version of the article, then published on the German review on 11 May 1926 (F.N.M.31).⁹⁰

The ‘ante quem’ limit of Fermi’s quantum statistics may therefore be set at the beginning of February 1926.

⁸⁶ “[...] si ottiene una degenerazione di un atteso ordine di grandezza solo se si sceglie il recipiente di dimensioni così piccole che esso in media contenga soltanto una molecola”.

⁸⁷ “Helium was only understood after quantum mechanical methods could be brought to bear, including important applications of spin and of the exclusion principle”, *cmp. PAIS* (1986), p. 215.

⁸⁸ *Cmp.* Rasetti’s introduction to F.N.M.30 and 31.

⁸⁹ For more information, *cmp. CORDELLA, SEBASTIANI* (1999)_fe (2000)_c.

⁹⁰ *Cmp.* Rasetti’s introduction to F.N.M.30 and 31. Otherwise AMALDI (1983), p. 253. From an immediate analysis of the Italian version of the article it’s evident that Fermi had already reached all the important results of his new statistics.

Fermi was very busy finding a post as a teacher (in February 1926 he participated unsuccessfully to an examination for a mathematical physics teaching post in Cagliari)⁹¹. Fermi's letter to Uhlenbeck and Goudsmit, dated 25 February 1926, stood between the two versions of the article:

“Since I came away from Holland, I was unfortunately always very busy so that I couldn't work very much and I was forced to be satisfied with the readings of reviews. Recently I have prepared two works, one on the quantization of an ideal gas, the other on the apparition of the forbidden transitions in a magnetic field; I'll send you the abstracts as soon as I get them.”⁹²

As for the more important ‘post quem’ limit, Segrè states that Fermi, a few weeks after reading Pauli's work on the exclusion principle, was able to present at the Lincei, through Corbino,⁹³ an Italian version of the article.⁹⁴ However that may be, it is still in doubt when Fermi was acquainted with Pauli's article. This one appeared in the February-April 1925 number of the *Zeitschrift für Physik*,⁹⁵ so that Fermi could have known it at least since the spring of 1925. However, as showed in the previous chapter, during the spring of 1925 Fermi was busy carrying out experimental work with Rasetti. In July, Fermi was engaged with state examinations in Florence. Fermi spent the summer with Kronig and others in S. Vito di Cadore. That may be important because, as asserted by A. Pais, Kronig had been aware of the exclusion principle at least since January 1925.⁹⁶ Therefore a likely hypothesis is that Kronig talked to Fermi about it during the summer vacations in S.Vito. Anyway, in the various sources regarding Fermi before F.N.M.30, there is no trace of Pauli's principle, while Fermi was puzzled by the articles of Heisenberg, Born and Jordan on the new quantum mechanics.⁹⁷

⁹¹ Cmp. F.N.M., p. XXVII and SEGRÈ (1970), p. 40.

⁹² Cmp. A.H.Q.P. (60/6). “In der ganzen Zeit seit Ich von Holland weg kam, war ich leider immer sehr beschäftigt, so dass ich habe sehr wenig Arbeiten können und habe mich hauptsächlich mit dem Lesen der Zeitschriften begnügen müssen. Ich habe neulich zwei Arbeiten gemacht, die eine über die Quantelung idealer Gase die andere über das auftreten verbotene Übergänge in einem Magnetsfelde; ich werde Euch die Separata schicken, sobald ich sie bekomme” The second work to which Fermi refers is F.N.M.32: *Sopra l'intensità delle righe proibite nei campi magnetici intensi*, Rendiconti Lincei, 3 (1926), 478-483. In the letter Fermi congratulates them for the discovery of the spin.

⁹³ In the Rend. Acc. Lincei, Garbasso is mentioned as the member who presented Fermi's article.

⁹⁴ Cmp. SEGRÈ (1970), p. 42.

⁹⁵ Cmp. PAULI (1925).

⁹⁶ Cmp. PAIS (1986), p. 280.

⁹⁷ The T. S. Kuhn's interview to Persico and Rasetti reads: “[...] TSK: Did Fermi say anything that you remember about the matrix mechanics papers? R: Oh, Fermi tried to read them, but he could not understand them. He said, ‘I cannot do any. I don't see how I can use it, how I can do any calculation with these. I don't understand what's behind it.’ Oh, he read them and he was very much puzzled by

Rasetti remembers an event (also recalled by Laura Fermi) occurred when Fermi was making his gas statistics: “We were practically together from morning till evening, from discussing physics to hunting for certain geckos, a sort of lizard [...]. That was precisely when he was making the gas statistics. He was probably thinking while lying down and catching the geckos with the noose”.⁹⁸ In Central Italy, at the end of September geckos usually hibernate.⁹⁹

Therefore, the ‘post quem’ limit of Fermi’s statistics, less precisely of the ‘ante quem’ limit, is roughly set in mid- September 1925.

ABBREVIATIONS

A.H.Q.P. (x/y) = “Archive for History of Quantum Physics”, microfilm x , section y .

AMAL. ARCH. (x/y) = “Amaldi Archive”, Department of Physics, University “La Sapienza”, Rome, box x , folder y .

PERS. ARCH. (x/y) = “Persico Archive”, Department of Physics, University “La Sapienza”, Rome, box x , folder y .

VOLT. ARCH. (x/y) = “Volterra Archive”, Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei, Rome, box x , folder y .

F.N.M. k = FERMI (1962-1965), vol. I., the k th work.

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them. **P**: I don’t remember that I ever discussed them with Fermi. **R**: I know that he showed me these papers and said, ‘Now I’m trying to read them and see what Heisenberg is trying to say, but so far I don’t understand it.’”, cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T. S. Kuhn (**TSK**) with F. Rasetti (**R**) and E. Persico (**P**), 8 April 1963, p. 16.

⁹⁸ Cmp. A.H.Q.P. transcript of a tape recorded interview by T. S. Kuhn with F. Rasetti and E. Persico, 8 April 1963, p. 13.

⁹⁹ M. Di Domenico, collaborator of the Zoology Department of the Istituto dell’Enciclopedia Italiana, private communication.

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